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**Vanja Radolić
Marina Poje Sovilj
Ines Krajcar Bronić**

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RADIONUCLIDES IN DRINKING WATER AND RISK ASSESSMENT

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INTRODUCTION

²³⁸U series radionuclides are the major contributors to the radiation dose caused by natural radionuclides ingested with drinking water [1]. The most important of these nuclides is ²²²Rn and some long-lived nuclides include ²³⁸U, ²³⁴U, ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ²¹⁰Pb and ²¹⁰Po. Because of its potential public health hazard, the surveys of radioactivity in water sources are necessary.

In this paper content of natural radioactive isotopes: ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ²³⁸U and artificial radioisotope ¹³⁷Cs in 40 samples of drinking water from the territory of Vojvodina (from water supplies, wells, fountains and from wellsprings) were determined. The annual effective dose due to consumption of these waters was estimated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The radionuclide content of the drinking water samples was determined from a cumulative sample by gamma-spectrometry measurements using the HPGe spectrometer made by Canberra. The nominal efficiency of the detector is 36% and the resolution is 1.9 keV. The detector was operated inside the 12 cm thick lead shield with the 3 mm Cu inner layer. The sample measurement time was 50 ks. The detector was connected to the digital spectroscopy processing unit Canberra 1300 InSpector. The gamma spectra were acquired and analyzed using the Canberra Genie 2000 software. All measurement uncertainties are presented at a 95 % confidence level [2].

The contribution of drinking-water to total exposure is typically very small and is due largely to naturally occurring radionuclides in the uranium and thorium decay series [3]. For drinking water radioactivity total

indicative dose TID (effective dose from radionuclides in drinking water except ^3H , ^{40}K , radon and radon progenies) is $0.1 \text{ mSv year}^{-1}$ [4].

The guidance levels GL for radionuclides in drinking water [3] were calculated by the equation:

$$\text{GL} = \frac{\text{IDC}}{h_{\text{ing}} \cdot q} \quad (1)$$

where IDC is individual dose criterion; equal to $0.1 \text{ mSv year}^{-1}$, h_{ing} is dose coefficient for ingestion by adults (mSv Bq^{-1}) and q is annual ingested volume of drinking water, assumed to be 730 l year^{-1} [3]. The guidance levels for ^{238}U , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{137}Cs are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Guidance levels GL for radionuclides in drinking water [3]

Radionuclide	GL (Bq l^{-1})
^{238}U	10
^{226}Ra	1
^{232}Th	1
^{137}Cs	10

An estimate of committed effective dose for each radionuclide should be made and the sum of these doses determined. If the following additive formula is satisfied, no further action is required:

$$\sum_i \frac{C_i}{\text{GL}_i} \leq 1 \quad (2)$$

For the analyzed radionuclides activity concentration in the water samples (C_i) dose calculations were carried out. The total dose (GD) is the sum of the dose contributions of the single radionuclides (GD_i), which are calculated from the activity concentrations (C_i) with the legal valid dose conversion factors ($h(g_i)$) for adults respectively and an annual consumption (KM) of 730 l year^{-1} [5].

$$\text{GD} = \sum_i \text{GD}_i = \sum_i h(g_i) \cdot C_i \cdot \text{KM} \quad (3)$$

Dose conversion factors ($h(g_i)$) are $4.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Sv Bq}^{-1}$ for ^{238}U ; $2.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ Sv Bq}^{-1}$ for ^{226}Ra ; $2.3 \times 10^{-7} \text{ Sv Bq}^{-1}$ for ^{232}Th and $1.3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Sv Bq}^{-1}$ for ^{137}Cs [5]. According to [6] the derived concentrations of individual radionuclides

in drinking water are $3.0 \text{ Bq}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ for ^{238}U , $4.9\times 10^{-1} \text{ Bq}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ for ^{226}Ra , $5.9\times 10^{-1} \text{ Bq}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ for ^{232}Th and $10.0 \text{ Bq}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ for ^{137}Cs .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the gamma-spectrometric measurement of the 40 water samples from Vojvodina are presented in Table 2. All water samples were sampled by Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina using ISO 5667 [7] standard method and measured in Department of Physics in Novi Sad.

Table 2. Results of radioactivity of drinking water and calculated total dose GD.

No	Water sample	$C_i^{137}\text{Cs}$ [Bq l ⁻¹]	$C_i^{226}\text{Ra}$ [Bq l ⁻¹]	$C_i^{232}\text{Th}$ [Bq l ⁻¹]	$C_i^{238}\text{U}$ [Bq l ⁻¹]	GD [mSv y ⁻¹]
1	Mladenovo	< 0.29	0.69(15)	0.38(14)	1(2)	0.11(4)
2	Nova Gajdobra	< 0.3	0.54(19)	0.22(13)	< 5	0.07(2)
3	Gajdobra	< 0.3	0.77(12)	0.09(9)	< 2.1	0.086(14)
4	Srbobran	< 0.29	0.37(12)	0.27(14)	2.2(25)	0.10(4)
5	Bački Jarak	< 0.3	0.65(18)	0.57(19)	1.1(19)	0.13(4)
6	Temerin	< 0.29	0.32(11)	0.17(12)	2.5(22)	0.09(4)
7	Sirig	< 0.3	0.85(27)	0.37(17)	1.6(19)	0.14(4)
8	Silbaš	< 0.3	0.34(12)	0.06(14)	0.8(22)	0.05(4)
9	Pivnice	< 0.3	0.50(12)	0.38(19)	5.6(23)	0.17(4)
10	Parage	< 0.29	0.38(13)	< 0.13	< 4	0.039(13)
11	Đurđevo	< 0.29	0.78(18)	0.05(14)	3.5(16)	0.14(3)
12	Žabalj	< 0.28	0.66(13)	0.14(15)	1(1)	0.092(25)
13	Čurug	< 0.3	0.3(13)	0.06(15)	2(3)	0.07(5)
14	Neštin	< 0.3	0.33(18)	< 0.15	1.8(11)	0.063(26)
15	Vizić	< 0.3	0.98(18)	0.14(14)	1.7(12)	0.14(3)
16	Novi Sad 1300 kaplara	< 0.29	0.7(3)	0.31(15)	< 1.3	0.10(3)
17	Novi Sad Jožefa Marčoka	< 0.28	0.89(14)	0.17(13)	2.0(19)	0.14(4)
18	Novi Sad Bul. Cara Lazara	< 0.2	0.25(9)	0.2(2)	0.8(8)	0.055(23)
19	Novi Sad, Ribarsko ostrvo	< 0.3	0.79(2)	0.39(14)	0.2(18)	0.12(4)
20	Novi Sad Balzakova	< 0.3	1.05(24)	0.18(15)	2(12)	0.16(3)
21	Novi Sad Narodnog fronta	< 0.28	0.72(15)	0.33(19)	0.1(13)	0.10(3)
22	Novi Sad Alberta Tome	< 0.3	0.70(22)	0.37(14)	< 4	0.103(25)

No	Water sample	$C_i^{137}\text{Cs}$ [Bq l ⁻¹]	$C_i^{226}\text{Ra}$ [Bq l ⁻¹]	$C_i^{232}\text{Th}$ [Bq l ⁻¹]	$C_i^{238}\text{U}$ [Bq l ⁻¹]	GD [mSv y ⁻¹]
23	Petrovaradin	< 0.3	0.16(11)	0.44(16)	0.6(9)	0.063(23)
24	Srbobran 2	< 0.28	0.18(19)	0.04(13)	0.3(13)	0.03(3)
25	Turija	< 0.3	0.58(25)	0.19(16)	5.8(25)	0.17(5)
26	Nadalj	< 0.29	0.54(12)	0.3(4)	0.2(14)	0.08(4)
27	Bački Petrovac	< 0.28	0.45(11)	<0.16	1.6(17)	0.07(3)
28	Kulpin	< 0.3	0.50(16)	0.54(25)	1.6(12)	0.12(3)
29	Bački Maglič	< 0.20	0.70(9)	0.16(1)	1.3(16)	0.106(29)
30	Zmajevo	< 0.29	2.2(4)	0.38(12)	0.4(21)	0.26(5)
31	Sremska Mitrovica I	< 0.3	7.8(3)	0.38(2)	2.2(24)	0.87(5)
32	Sremska Mitrovica II	< 0.3	3.67(17)	0.31(9)	4.0(23)	0.47(4)
33	Sremska Mitrovica III	< 0.29	1.36(11)	0.29(1)	0.3(2)	0.17(4)
34	Sremska Mitrovica IV	< 0.3	1.7(13)	0.36(1)	1.9(15)	0.235(29)
35	Sremska Mitrovica V	< 0.3	1.33(16)	<0.08	< 4	0.136(16)
36	Čalma	< 0.3	1.77(14)	0.04(15)	< 4	0.184(19)
37	Divoš	< 0.3	1.79(13)	0.49(1)	< 5	0.224(16)
38	Ležimir	< 0.3	1.58(24)	0.62(11)	0.8(11)	0.23(3)
39	Šuljam	< 0.3	1.01(17)	0.87(12)	2.9(23)	0.22(4)
40	Beš. Prnjavor	< 0.29	1.21(18)	0.29(9)	0.1(2)	0.15(4)

Recommended radionuclide parameters for drinking water assessment for ^{226}Ra for monitoring is 0.5 Bq l⁻¹, and for intervention is 5.0 Bq l⁻¹ [4]. Comparing the measured result for ^{226}Ra from Table 2 it can be concluded that activity concentration of ^{226}Ra in 32 investigated water samples exceeded legally established level for ^{226}Ra content in drinking water [4,6] from monitoring, and in one sample from Sremska Mitrovica (No. 31, Table 2) exceeded level for intervention [6]. In samples No 9, 11, 25 and 32, ^{238}U concentration is higher than the reference level of 3.0 Bq·l⁻¹ [6]. Activity concentrations of ^{232}Th in two samples (No. 38 and 39, Table 2) are higher than recommended [6]. Radioisotope ^{137}Cs in water samples is not detected. In 23 investigated samples total dose GD from radionuclides in drinking water is higher than 0.1 mSv year⁻¹ [4].

CONCLUSION

The radionuclide content of the drinking water samples from Vojvodina region was determined by gamma-spectrometry. The activity concentrations for ^{226}Ra in 32 of investigated samples are higher than the legally established levels for radionuclide content in drinking water in Serbia [6]. In four water samples concentration of ^{238}U is higher than recommended, and in two samples activity concentration of ^{232}Th is higher than the reference value [6]. In 23 investigated samples total dose GD from radionuclides in drinking water is higher than $0.1 \text{ mSv year}^{-1}$ [4]. From the obtained results it can be concluded that these waters are not safe for consumption from radioactivity point of view.

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Drinking water can contain radioactive isotopes which represent potential risk to human health. In case of nuclear accident and uncontrolled releasing radionuclides from nuclear power plants, it is necessary to rapidly implement control of radioactivity level in the surrounding waters, air and soil.

Method of gamma spectroscopy analysis in scientific research is one of the most common experimental methods for quantitative analysis of radioactivity content in the samples. In this paper content of natural radioactive isotopes: ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K, ²³⁸U and artificial radioisotope ¹³⁷Cs in 40 samples of drinking water from the territory of Vojvodina (from water supplies, wells, fountains and from wellsprings) were determined. The annual effective dose due to consumption of these waters was estimated. Based on the results, it was concluded that most samples contain activity concentration of ²²⁶Ra over the legally regulated values. In 23 investigated samples, total dose GD from radionuclides in drinking water is higher than 0.1 mSv year⁻¹.